

Western Blotting of WT-OE cell lines

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Protocol description

Western Blotting of the RESOLUTE WTOE cell lines to check for protein expression.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ RESOLUTE WT-OE cell line▪ PNGase F (NEB, P0704L)▪ Cyclophilin B antibody (abcam ab178397)▪ HRP conjugated anti-HA-7 (Sigma H6533)▪ HRP conjugated anti-rabbit IgG (Jackson ImmonuResearch 111-035-003)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Blasticidin (Invivogen, ant-bl-5b)▪ Geneticin/G418 (Sigma-Aldrich, A1720)▪ Doxycycline hyclate (Sigma-Aldrich, D9891)▪ NP-40 alternative (VWR, 492016)▪ HEPES (Lactan, 9105.3)▪ NaCl (Sigma-Aldrich, S7653)▪ EDTA (Sigma-Aldrich, E6758)▪ Roche cOmplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Sigma-Aldrich, 5056489001)▪ DTT (Sigma-Aldrich, 43819)▪ BCA Protein Assay Kit (VWR, PIER23225)▪ Bromphenol Blue (Sigma-Aldrich, B-7021)▪ Glycerol (Merck, 1.04201.5000)▪ Sodiumdodecylsulfate (SDS) (Serva, 20765)▪ Tris[hydroxymethyl]aminomethane (Sigma-Aldrich, T-1503)▪ Glycine (Merck, 1.04201.5000)▪ Methanol >99.8% (Sigma-Aldrich, 65543)▪ TBS Buffer (Sigma-Aldrich, 274348)▪ Tween-20 (Sigma-Aldrich, 274348)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ SpectraMax i3x (Molecular Devices)▪ Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System (Bio-Rad, 1704150)▪ Nitrocellulose transfer membrane (A. Hartenstein, NC04)▪ Chromatographie Bögen 3MM;460x570,Whatman, (VWR, 514-8013)▪ Amersham Hyperfilm ECL (Merck, 28-9068-37)

	▪ ECL Plus Western Blotting Detection Reagents (GE Healthcare, RPN2132)
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Reagents setup

50 mg/ml stock solution of Geneticin

Dissolve 5 g of Geneticin in 100 ml of ddH₂O and sterilize through a 0.22- μ m filter and store at 4°C.

10 mg/ml stock solution of Doxycycline hyclate

Dissolve 100 mg of doxycycline in 10 ml of 70% ethanol and sterilize through a 0.22- μ m filter. Store 100 μ l aliquots at -20°C.

Lysis buffer E1A (store at 4°C)

1% NP-40 alternative,
50 mM HEPES pH 7.4,
250 mM NaCl,
5 mM EDTA

Lämmli Sample Buffer (4 \times , store at -20°C)

20 mL 0.5 M Tris-HCl pH 6.8
20 mL glycerol
4 g SDS
10 mL water
0.008% Bromphenol blue

SDS Running Buffer (10 \times)

250 mM Tris, 1,9 M Glycine, 35 mM SDS
602 g Tris[hydroxymethyl]aminomethane (Tris)
2880 g Glycine
200 g SDS
Add water to 20 L

Transfer Buffer (10 \times)

121.4 g Tris [hydroxymethyl]aminomethane
576.8 g Glycine
Add MilliQ Water up to 4 L

Transfer Buffer (Semi-Dry, store at 4°C)

50 ml 10 \times Transfer Buffer
50 ml MeOH

400 ml H₂O

Procedure

▪ Harvesting Cells

1. Grow cells for 5-7 days with selection medium containing 2 mg/ml Geneticin and 5 µg/ml Blasticidin
2. Seed 1 million cells / well (in a 6-well plate) in 3 ml DMEM 10% FBS, 1%P/S (HEK cells, change to appropriate medium for your cells).
3. For inducible cells: Induce expression by adding 1 µg/ml Doxycycline – containing medium.
4. Incubate cells for 24 h at 37°C after induction
5. Wash cells with 1 ml PBS to remove serum proteins.
6. Harvest cells by pipetting up and down in 800 µl of PBS containing Complete Protease inhibitor cocktail (1x)
7. Centrifuge 3000 rpm RT for 5 min
8. Remove supernatant
9. Resuspend cells pipetting up-and-down in cold E1A lysis buffer containing Roche Complete protease inhibitor. Lysis buffer volume depends on the nature of the cells, for HEK293 use 70 µl lysis buffer / well of a 6-well plate. → the volume depends on the size of the pellet. If the pellet is very small, use less. If the solution is viscous after adding 70 µl, add ~30 to 40 µl more.
10. Incubate Lysates on ice for 30 min
11. Centrifuge sample for 15 minutes 4°C at max. speed (14.000 rpm) in a table top centrifuge.
12. Transfer supernatants to fresh tubes and freeze.

▪ Protein Quantification

1. Protein quantification with BCA.
2. use 5 µl of the protein standards by Thermo Fisher, (from 0.125 µg/µl to 2 µg/µl) in two replicates and 5 µl of E1A buffer as a blank
3. dilute the samples 1:5
4. transfer 5 µl of the dilution to the BCA plate
5. mix the BCA solutions in a ratio of 1:50
6. add 100 µl of BCA mix per well
7. close plate with adhesive lid, shake for 1 min
8. incubate the plate for 30 min at 37°C
9. measure in a spectrometer

▪ **PNGase treatment (only for Dox induced samples)**

10. Add 1.5 μ l of Glycobuffer 2

1. Add 25 μ g of protein according to BCA quantification
2. Add 1 μ l of PNGaseF
3. Add water to a final volume of 15 μ l
4. Incubate at 37°C o/n

▪ **SDS-PAGE**

1. For samples after PNGaseF treatment: Add 5 μ l of Lamli Buffer to the plate (+DTT; 250 μ l of Buffer + 0.015 mg of DTT) and spin down the plate
2. For samples that do not need PNGase treatment: 5 μ l of Lamli Buffer + the amount of cell lysate necessary to have 20 μ of total protein + H₂O up to 20 μ l.
3. Incubate for 10 min at 65°C in the PCR machine.
4. Load the total samples in a SDS-PAGE gel (8- 12% Acrylamide-Bisacrylamide)
5. Run gel (in 1x running buffer): 100-150 V until blue line reaches lower edge of glass

▪ **Western Blot with Bio-Rad Transfer Machine:**

1. Prepare 12 pieces of Whatman paper and one membrane per SDS-Gel
2. Soak the membranes and Whatman paper in transfer buffer for 5 min
3. Place 6 pieces of Whatman paper into the tray of the machine, put the membrane on top, then the gel, then place 6 pieces of Whatman paper on top
4. Use the roller to remove air bubbles
5. Empty out excess transfer buffer from tray
6. Run the gel with the Standard programme for 30 min
7. Transfer the membrane to Ponceau to check equal loading
8. Wash off Ponceau directly in TBS-T (2 min washing), take a picture, wash in milk to remove the rest of the Ponceau (~5 min)
9. Block for 1 h in 5% milk in TBS-T, shaking at RT
10. Cut membrane into two pieces at 25 KDa. The piece of membrane that contains proteins above 25KDa (1) will be used for immunodetection of the bait proteins, and the other one (2) will be used for loading control using cyclophilin-B)
11. Incubate the membrane 1 with α -HA7 HRP 1:7000 in 5% Milk TBS-T at 4°C in a falcon overnight. Note: check that the membranes are marked so that afterwards membranes can be associated with protein.
12. Incubate membrane protein 2 with α -cyclophilinB 1:5000 (Rabbit) in 5% Milk TBS-T at 4°C in a falcon overnight
13. wash each membrane 3x in TBS-T (15 min each), each time discard TBS-T and replace by new buffer

14. Incubation of membrane 2 with secondary antibody anti-rabbit HRP coupled Ab 1:5000 in milk), 1 h in a falcon at RT.
15. Wash 3x in TBS-T
16. Develop both membranes using 1:1 mix of ECL solutions

Additional notes

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.